

THE ROLE OF INTEGRATION IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS OF PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

Toshpulatova Mamurakhon Ismoilovna

Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences
associate professor of the department

"Mathematics and its teaching methodology in primary education"
at the Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizomi,
m.tashpulatova@mail.ru, +998935615929
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7710389>

The changes taking place in the educational system of Uzbekistan, mediated by socio-economic transformations in the country, led to the realization of the need to find ways to update the professional development of teachers. Particularly significant in these conditions is the formation of a specialist's competencies, including his personal and professional qualities, and hence his ability to live and work in new conditions [2]. The teacher's readiness for integrative-pedagogical activity in teaching younger students is a necessary condition for the successful and productive activity of a modern primary school teacher, determining the nature of her approaches to solving urgent problems posed to elementary school by a student-oriented paradigm of education.

In modern trends in primary education, one of the pressing problems is the need for integration as the essence of the formation of a new content and forms of its organization, and as a basis that dynamizes the educational process. To start the development and self-development of the essential, natural properties of the individual, in their unity and integrity - this is the main reason for the need for pedagogical integration in the modern educational process of elementary school. In our study, the essential concept of "pedagogical integration" was clarified, which is interpreted as a process and result of the development, formation and formation of a multidimensional human integrity in the context of the implementation of integrative and pedagogical activities in elementary school [1].

Using a holistic and systematic approach and recognizing the priority of the child's personality as the highest value and meaning of education, as a source of its development, we have formulated the criteria for the components of the content of the modern cultural and educational space of elementary school: activity, student-oriented, conceptual, problematic, alternative (variable), national-regional, integrated subject content. These criteria in the conditions of an integrative organization will ensure the holistic development of the personality and the worldview of a growing person. Thus, an attempt was made

to formulate the concepts of “content integration” (in education), “integrated learning”, the types of content integration were identified, its levels and factors were specified, and the mechanism for its implementation in the educational space of a younger student was identified.

In the studies of domestic and foreign scientists, various methods and a set of theoretical and practical provisions are proposed for the effective implementation of integration processes in the system of advanced training of primary school teachers. They presented the problem of pedagogical integration in educational programs of variable and problem-based advanced training courses for primary school teachers as the main component of the content of all blocks of the program and as a way to implement this content, provided with adequate integration technologies. To do this, researchers conducted analyzes of the content of the advanced training program for primary school teachers, revealed interdisciplinary connections between pedagogy, psychology and frequent teaching methods. Thus, scientists-researchers concluded that the integration of content is possible not only at the level of knowledge, but also at the level of general methods of activity and intellectual technologies. Since the integration of content is associated with a change in the structure of training sessions, the organizational technologies of the educational process of the advanced training system can become factors in the integration of content [3].

Thus, the changes taking place in the educational system of primary education, associated with the modernization of the structure and content, in a new way determine the role and place of the primary school teacher, his professional readiness. Particularly significant in these conditions is the teacher's readiness for integrative pedagogical activity in teaching younger students. The study substantiates the concept of "integrative-pedagogical activity", clarifies scientific ideas about the essence of the concept of "readiness" of primary school teachers for integrative-pedagogical activities in the field of integrating the content of the learning process [1]. The initial criteria for readiness for integrative pedagogical activity are the representation of value orientations in professional development: interest in the problem of content integration; personally meaningful meaning of conscious activity; knowledge of the leading means of integrating content, the formation of a system of skills (gnostic, design, constructive, organizational, communicative), the development of professional creativity.

Developed by domestic and foreign researchers, the conceptual model of professional development of primary school teachers on the formation and

development of the primary school teacher's readiness for integrative pedagogical activity is an integral system consisting of a set of modern methodological approaches, knowledge of pedagogical integration and ways to implement it in primary education, ensuring the integrity and evolution of pedagogical skills and pedagogical culture of primary school teachers. The presence of a theoretical and methodological vertical in this model allows it to organically combine fundamental, applied and personality-oriented functions that make possible a holistic, and therefore adequate, consideration of integrative pedagogical phenomena in the unity of their methodological, theoretical and practical parameters [2]. It is proved that that the decisive condition for the formation of readiness for integrative-pedagogical activity in the field of the content of the educational process in the professional development of primary school teachers is a multi-level three-stage approach to teaching students, reflecting the relationship and interaction of different components of education: motivational, content-didactic, organizational-activity, reflective creative. The degree of formation of readiness criteria for a primary school teacher made it possible to distinguish the following levels of readiness: reproductive, partially search, research, creative. Each level has a content characteristic that reflects the degree of completeness and effectiveness of the knowledge and skills acquired by teachers on pedagogical integration in the system of advanced training.

References:

1. Bokhodirova N.A. Integration of classroom and extracurricular activities in elementary school based on the project method // Actual tasks of pedagogy: materials of the VI Intern. scientific conf. (Kazan). 2022. - pp. 118-120.
2. The role of integration in the primary education system // <https://nsportal.ru/nachalnaya-shkola/materialy-mo/2020/06/21/rol-integratsii-v-sisteme-nachalnogo-obrazovaniya>
3. Shagina Z.V. Preparing a future primary school teacher for a conscious choice of a variable learning system: Dis. cand. ped. Sciences. Volgograd, 2004.

